

1 **Supplementary Information**

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3 Offspring sex ratio is affected by pre-breeding rainfall and hatching order in a cooperative
4 breeding bird

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6 **Table S1** Records for 10 smooth-billed ani nests monitored at the Cabo Rojo National Wildlife
7 Refuge in 2021. These data were used to estimate the onset of egg laying in cases where exact
8 dates were unavailable in our 2005 and 2011 – 2014 offspring sex ratio dataset.

Territory	First egg	First chick	Days elapsed
South Farm	7-Nov-21	3-Dec-21	27
Farm Entrance	10-Nov-21	7-Dec-21	28
Rickety Gate	10-Nov-21	6-Dec-21	27
Tamarind	11-Nov-21	13-Dec-21	33
Sandy Corner	12-Nov-21	7-Dec-21	26
West 4 Way	13-Nov-21	10-Dec-21	28
East Refuge Field	13-Nov-21	14-Dec-21	32
Pipeforest	14-Nov-21	10-Dec-21	27
Mango	15-Nov-21	14-Dec-21	30
N ²	17-Nov-21	12-Dec-21	26
			\bar{x} 28.4
			range 26 – 32

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11 **Fig. S1** Linear regression of the number of days from first egg laid to first chick hatched in 10
 12 joint-nests monitored daily in 2021 ($\bar{x} = 28.4$, range = 26 – 32). Axes units are expressed as
 13 calendar dates (Dec 1 – 20, Nov 5 – 20). Given the significant positive relationship ($F_{1, 8} = 10.6$,
 14 $p = 0.017$), we used 28 days from the date the first chick hatched to estimate the date the first
 15 eggs were laid in nests from 2005 and 2011 – 2014 with missing data. The egg laying start date
 16 was then used to calculate cumulative pre-breeding rainfall in the 30 days prior to the start of
 17 egg laying.

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29 **Fig. S2** Linear regression of tarsus length (to the nearest 0.1 mm) and chick age for 131 chicks of
30 known age sampled in the 2012 and 2013 breeding seasons ($R^2 = 87.4\%$, $F = 440.20$, $p =$
31 <0.001). Dotted lines indicate 95% confidence intervals. Figure provided by Colleen Bobbie and
32 used here with permission.